

TYPES OF MUSIC AS CORRELATE OF DEVIANT BEHAVIOUR AMONG UNDERGRADUATES IN SELECTED UNIVERSITY IN OGUN STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract

Background: There are several assumptions that youth behaviour (good or deviant) is related to the kind of music they listen to, this study therefore has investigated into the type of music and deviant behaviour among undergraduates. **Method:** Descriptive survey research design was used to examine if any significant relationship exists between choice of music and deviant behaviour amongst undergraduate students. Stratified random sampling method was used to select 269 participants from a private university in Ogun State Nigeria. Data was collected using a self-structured questionnaire that has alpha coefficient reliability of .76. **Findings:** revealed that the most selected music genre by the students is Hip-hop and the deviant behaviour associated with this genre is tattooing Rap music was observed to be strongly associated with deviant behaviours such as, drug abuse and examination malpractices, a significant relationship exist between Afro-beat and drug abuse. **Conclusion:** It was therefore concluded that the type of music listen to, is a contributing factor to deviant behaviour. The findings suggest that students should be encouraged to listen to music with lyrics that uphold virtues and musicians should produce music with lyrics that teach morals.

Keywords: Deviant Behaviour, Music, Musical Genre, Undergraduates, Youth

INTRODUCTION

The increasing level of deviant behaviours exhibited by adolescents at home, schools and the society at large has generated a great concern to parents, teachers, school administrators and even the government. It has become a common place for adolescents to engage in all forms of deviant behaviours such as violence, drug abuse, sexual immorality, cheating, bullying, and truancy among others. Amber (2012) described deviant behaviours as the violate social norms which can be divided into formal and informal. Formal deviant behaviours include robbery, theft, rape, murder, and assault while informal deviance includes picking one's nose, belching loudly, or standing unnecessarily close to another person. The formal deviant behaviours are the focus of this study.

Aderanti and Hassan (2011) also described deviant behaviour as the behaviour which goes against set or laid down rules of a particular entity. The common delinquent behaviours displayed by adolescents include smoking marijuana, prostitution, ingestion of alcohol and

other hard substances as well as sexual immorality. They therefore stressed that deviant behaviour is a social problem that cannot be overlooked due to negative effect on both the deviant and the society in general in that unchecked deviant can encourage many more children to act similarly.

Due to the role confusion and identity stage in the lives of these adolescents, as proposed by Erik Erikson, adolescents believe that standing out is doing what the rules tell them not to and they tend to act on peer influence and emulate lifestyles of those they consider as role models in order to be accepted into a social setting. Adolescents tend to fall as victims displaying deviant behaviours as they feel independent at a certain age and believe they can make major decisions on their own. Many of them have problems and are getting into trouble with school authority, parents or the society. Sometimes these adolescents cannot easily explain why they act the way they do. Any number of isolated behaviour problems can represent adolescent problems and delinquency-shoplifting, truancy, a fight in school, drug or alcohol ingestion, prostitution etc. (Anderson Carnagey, Eubanks 2016).

Several researchers have worked on various factors of deviant behaviours among adolescents. Such factors include socio-economic background (Connolly, Lewis, & Boisvert, 2017), gender (Olusakin 2000; Rebellon, Manasse, Agnew, Van Gundy, & Cohn, 2016), parenting styles (Okorodudu, 2010; Aderanti and Williams, 2010; Onsando, Mwenje, & Githui 2021), and the internet. However, this study examines music as a factor that contributed to deviant behaviour among adolescents.

The advancement of technology has contributed both positively and negatively to the adolescents' development. Adolescents often learn from what is seen and heard on the media. Most behavioural traits are portrayed in music, especially the lyrics of specific genre of songs produced and the musical videos. This study also tries to identify the genre of music that fuels adolescents' deviant behaviour.

Rogers (2016) carried out a study on the effect of music on one's behaviour and how each genre of music a person listened to over a period of time affect the thinking pattern and found out that listening to Metal music and Rock somewhat encourages militaristic and aggressive lifestyle; Blues and Jazz encourage relaxation, while classical, encourage the need to have information and knowledge. In other words, the type of music one listens to, takes root in the soul. Hence the music most adolescents occupy their minds with become a part of them; a habit which reflects in their behaviour. This implies that the music an adolescent listen to could to a large extent define the type of person he/she becomes. For example, Carson (2022) reported that some American leaders opined that rap music is the leading cause of violence and killing in the United State of America.

Music fulfils a range of functions for human beings. For example, music is said to regulate emotions by temporarily allowing an escape from thoughts and feelings or validating thoughts and feelings, and releasing stored up emotions, anxiety, energy and anger (Felicity and Williams, 2008; Olsen, Thompson, and Terry, 2022). While it is clear that music is a significant

part of the lives of adolescents, the evidence that certain music genre contributes to certain behaviours is being questioned.

The study of Sousou (2007) reveals that a number of youth drug victims had spent a lot of their time listening to Rap music that is often insinuated to instigate the use of drugs in their lyrics. The foregoing has been exemplified in the negative influence of Naira Marley's Mafo, Zlanta's Unripe Pawpaw and Olamide's Science Students on the Nigerian youths. Roe (1985), and observes that all kinds of music people listen to generally affect their personality and perception which in turn shape their behaviours, whether good or bad. Similarly Boundless (2020) observes that the kind of music youths listen to can have both positive and negative influence on their social and psychological well-being. In other words, music can be both therapeutic (improves the mood, promotes social life, and enhances their emotional states) and can lead to engagement in anti-social behaviour.

Although the power of music to act therapeutically has long been recognized, therapy can involve listening to or actively making music. Increasingly, it may involve both. Music can be effective in conjunction with other interventions in promoting relaxation, alleviating anxiety and pain in medicine and dentistry, and promoting well-being through the production of particular endorphins (Schaefer, 2017).

Music is a powerful tool useful for different occasions, purposes or mood-changes. Music exists in every culture; the ways people respond or react to it differ greatly with respect to the genres of music (Lozon and Bensimon, 2014). These responses or reactions to a large extent affect the general dispositions as evident in the adolescents. It is for these reasons that some societies are concerned about the types of music people listen to and also attempt to control its use considering its power at the level of the social group, how it facilitates communication which goes beyond words, enables meanings to be shared, and promotes the development and maintenance of individual, group, cultural and national identities. Music as observed by Smith (2005) is powerful at the individual level because it can induce multiple responses – physiological, movement, mood, emotional, cognitive and behavioural.

The lyrics of some music by certain artistes may influence the behaviour of an individual. Adolescents are at higher risk of becoming addicted to music. Often times, they prefer to stay alone, getting plugged to music on the radio, phone playlist, internet or even the ones which they might have recorded. When some individuals like a song, they experience “chills” and a “high” of sorts, which may give them a lot of energy and pleasurable feelings. Those who put songs on repeat all the time want to re-experience those sensations over and over again.

In addition to the “chills”, continuous listening to one's favourite music may also trigger the release of dopamine, a neurotransmitter that plays a role in underlying pleasurable reactions caused by food, drugs and arousal before intercourse. For example, Bogt cited in Anderson (2017) carried out a longitudinal study on 309 children (149 boys and 160 girls) and their families in Netherland, following up on teens from age 12 until they turned 16 and figured the children's interests in various types of music like rock, African-American music, electronic

dance music, highbrow music and conventional pop as they grew. It was revealed that teens that preferred this genre of music tend to act delinquently.

The concern of this study is to investigate, if all forms of adolescent misdemeanours are the resultant effect of the types of music they listen to. The main objective of this study is to investigate the relationship between the type of music adolescents listen to and deviant behaviour.

Research Questions

1. What types of musical genres are preferred by the undergraduate students?
2. How frequent do undergraduates listen to these musical genres?
3. Will the type of music listen to by adolescents engender deviant behaviour?

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was used for this study in order to examine the relationship between independent variable (music choice) and dependent variable (deviant behaviour). Participants consist of 269 undergraduates in a selected university in the southwest Nigeria using stratified random sampling technique. The instrument used for this study was a self-structured questionnaire which was divided into four sections. Section A contains items on the demographic information of the respondents, Section B contains items on choice of music preferred, and Section C was on the types of music listen to, while Section D is on Deviant behaviour. A test re-test reliability of the instrument was carried out. The instrument was found to be reliable with the alpha coefficient of .76. Data collected was analysed using percentages, and Pearson Product Moment correlation coefficient at 0.05 level of significant.

Results

Research Question 1: What types of musical genres are preferred by the undergraduate students?

Table 1: Distribution of respondent's musical choices

Music genre	Frequency	Percentage
Foreign hip hop	189	83.2
Nigerian hip hop	166	73.1
Rock	93	40.9
Rap	143	63.0
Rhythm and blues	108	47.5
Afro beats	98	42.8
Juju	53	23.3
Fuji	62	27.3
Apala	32	14.1
Gospel	165	72.7

Table 1 gives an insight into the musical genres mostly preferred by the respondents of this study. It is shown here that foreign Hip hop (83.2%) is the most preferred type of music adopted by the study participants. This preference is closely followed by Nigerian Hip hop (73.1%) and Gospel music (72.1%). In this study, Apala music was the least preferred type of music which was indicated by only 14.1 percent of the study population.

Research Question 2: How frequent do Undergraduates listen to these musical genres?

Table 2: Frequency of usage of different music genres

Music genre	Frequency by which music is listened to			
	Very frequently N (%)	Frequently N (%)	Seldom N (%)	Not at all N (%)
Foreign hip hop	126 (55.5)	55 (24.2)	25 (11.0)	8 (3.5)
Nigerian hip hop	93 (41.0)	58 (25.6)	36 (15.9)	24 (10.6)
Rock	30 (13.2)	49 (21.6)	48 (21.1)	65 (28.6)
Rap	67 (29.5)	65 (28.6)	36 (15.9)	30 (13.2)
R and B	50 (22.0)	58 (25.6)	28 (12.3)	55 (24.2)
Afrobeats	33 (14.5)	50 (22.0)	49 (21.6)	54 (23.8)
Juju	17 (7.5)	29 (12.8)	34 (15.0)	104 (45.8)
Fuji	17 (7.5)	25 (11.0)	50 (22.0)	91 (40.1)
Apala	10 (4.4)	16 (7.0)	31 (13.7)	120 (52.9)
Gospel	106 (46.7)	49 (21.6)	28 (12.3)	30 (13.2)

Table 2 displays how regular the study participants listen to different music genres. It is seen here that the music that is mostly preferred seem to also have a very regular frequency by which they are heard by the respondents. For example, 55.5 percent of the participants listen to foreign Hip hop very frequently, while 46.7 percent of the participants listen to Gospel music. 52.9 percent of the study population have not heard Apala music before while 45.8 percent of the participants were yet to listen to any Juju song.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between choice of music and deviant behaviour of undergraduate students

Table 3: Relationship between music choice and deviant behaviours

		Music	Deviant
Music Choice	Pearson Correlation	1	.151*
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.033
	N	204	199
Deviant	Pearson Correlation	.151*	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.033	
	N	199	204

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Table 3 shows a significant relationship between independent variable -Music choice and dependent variable - deviant behaviour ($r = .151$; $p = .033$). This implies that choice of music may result into deviant behaviour.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between the type of music listened to and deviant behaviours of undergraduates

Table 4: Relationship between type of music listened to and deviant behaviours among respondents

Music choice	Deviant behaviours					
	Bullying	Drug abuse	Disobedience to authority	Rape	Have tattooing	Exam malpractice
Foreign hip hop	0.999	0.162	0.886	1.000	0.027*	0.657
Nigerian hip hop	0.895	0.957	0.837	1.000	0.991	0.383
Rock	0.952	0.798	0.976	0.790	1.000	0.965
Rap	0.997	0.000*	0.083	0.866	0.767	0.039*
Rhythm and blues	0.926	0.656	0.940	0.990	0.443	0.543
Afro beats	0.468	0.023*	0.745	0.562	0.270	0.265
Juju	0.811	0.750	0.892	0.782	0.078	0.921
Fuji	0.537	0.361	0.953	0.976	0.999	0.831
Apala	0.402	0.192	0.445	0.220	0.795	0.536
Gospel	0.877	0.081	0.352	0.993	0.201	0.961

*significant at $p < 0.05$

Table 4 shows the association that exists between the musical choices of the respondents and the deviant behaviours they exhibit. The result shows a strong significant relationship between Foreign Hip hop ($P = 0.027$) and tattooing, while significant relationship exist between Rap music and some deviant behaviours such as drug abuse ($P = 0.002$), and examination

malpractice ($P = 0.037$). Also, a significant relationship exists between Afro beat and drug abuse ($P = 0.023$). This implies that people who listen to foreign hip hop music have the tendency to tattoo their body, while people who listen to Rap music are more likely to abuse drugs and engage in examination malpractices while those who listen to Afro beat are more likely to engage in drug abuse.

DISCUSSION

In this study it was observed that Hip hop music was the most preferred genre of music among the respondents of this study. This is expected, as the Hip hop genre seems to be the favorite of majority of young people since its inception. This study though carried out among some youths in Nigeria confirms the year-end report of Nielsen Music's 2017 cited in Ryan (2018) that R&B/hip-hop has surpassed rock to become the biggest music genre in the U.S. in terms of total consumption.

According to Spotify analysis of 20 billion tracks, Hip hop was observed to be the most patronized musical genre in the world showing up on playlists more than all others, regardless of culture. The popularity of Hip hop music could be as a result of various reasons including its inclusiveness with other genres such as Rap, Rock, R&B, Soul, among others.

The main objective of this study was to evaluate the relationship that exists between the genres of music listened to by the respondents and the various deviant behaviors common to them. It was observed in this study that Rap music was strongly associated with some deviant behaviors such as examination malpractice, and drug abuse. One of the reasons that could explain this outcome is the lyrical effect on the listeners. These lyrics have become more explicit in their references to drugs, sex, and violence over the years. A content analysis of the top 10 CDs performed by the National Institute on Media in 1999 revealed that each of these CDs included at least 1 song with sexual content. Forty-two percent of the songs on these CDs contained very explicit sexual content (Gentile 1999). Lyrics of some music genres, such as Rock, Heavy metal, Rap, some have been found to revolve around topics such as sexual promiscuity, death, homicide, suicide, and substance abuse. Some Rap songs have been characterized by the presence of explicit sexual language in its lyrics as well as messages of violence, racism, homophobia, and hatred toward women. Drug, tobacco, and alcohol use also tend to be glorified in these songs (Diamond et al. 2006). Rap music is also usually associated with partying in which many of these deviant behaviours thrive. This study also established association between Afrobeat and drug abuse among the respondents. Afrobeat, although an African rooted genre, has in recent time been influenced by western styles and lyrics which in turn tends to have corrupting effects on its listeners.

CONCLUSION

Although Hip hop was the commonly preferred genre of music, as the study revealed, rap, a hybrid of hip hop is shown to be the most associated with misbehaviours among the respondents. The appreciation of gospel music was low among the participants. It was

therefore concluded that the music most adolescents occupy their minds with is reflected in their behaviour.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended that youths as well as adolescents should be encouraged to listen to songs with good lyrics that can inspire them to good works and since most undergraduates have the tendency to constantly listen to music even within the framework of academic rigors, there is the need for proper orientation on their musical selections that will enhance assimilation and good disposition toward good behaviour. Also, the government, policy makers and regulatory agencies should censor the lyrical contents of music before their release to the general public, and erring music outlets should be sanctioned or totally blocked. Finally, public awareness and sensitization campaign should be created to warn the youths about the possible harmful effects of exposure to perverse and corruptive lyrical contents that could predispose them to vices and other deviant behaviours.

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